

ALL-ISLAND CANCER DATA FORUM

26th & 27th January 2026, Queen's University Belfast

Prof. Ian Bruce

Pro Vice Chancellor Medicine, Health and Life Sciences Queen's University Belfast

Topic: Welcome and Opening Remarks

Time: Monday, 26th January, 10:00-10:05

Speaker Profile: Professor Ian Bruce is Professor of Rheumatology and an NIHR Senior Investigator, with clinical practice at Manchester University NHS Foundation Trust. He is Director of the NIHR Manchester Biomedical Research Centre and Academic Director of Health Innovation Manchester, and also serves as Pro-Vice-

Chancellor for the Faculty of Medicine, Health and Life Sciences at Queen's University Belfast. His research focuses on systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis, and long-term cardiovascular outcomes in inflammatory rheumatic disease.

Prof. Mark Lawlor

Professor of Digital Health, Queen's University Belfast & Co-Lead All-Island ehealth Hub for Cancer

Topic: Data trump opinion...every time

Time: Monday, 26th January, 10:05-10:25

Speaker Profile: Professor Lawlor is an internationally renowned cancer researcher with over 30 years' experience, recognised for translating research into patient, clinical, and policy impact. He is Scientific Director of DATA-CAN (UK Health Data Research Hub for Cancer) and Associate Director of Health Data Research Wales–

Northern Ireland. He was the architect of the European Cancer Patient's Bill of Rights and the 70:35 Vision for cancer survival, and his research in colorectal cancer and cancer health data has influenced practice and policy across Europe.

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Limerick Digital Cancer Research Centre

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Margaret Grayson MBE

Patient Advocate, Northern Ireland Cancer Research Consumer Forum (NICRCF)

Topic: My Data! Use It?

Time: Monday, 26th January, 10:25-10:35

Speaker Profile: Margaret is a patient advocate who believes excellence in health and social care depends on high-quality data, clinical research, and strong patient partnership. Diagnosed with breast cancer in 2004 (and again in 2021), she brings lived experience to her advocacy work. A former NHS therapy

radiographer from Belfast, she now partners with a wide range of research organisations across the UK and Ireland to strengthen public involvement in health research. In recognition of her services to cancer research, she was awarded an MBE in the 2018 Queen's Birthday Honours.

Prof. Aedin Culhane

Professor of Cancer Genomics, University of Limerick & Co-Lead All-Island ehealth Hub for Cancer

Topic: From Fragmented Data Silos to Actionable Evidence for Care

Time: Monday, 26th January, 10:35 - 10:55

Speaker Profile: Aedín C. Culhane is Professor of Cancer Genomics at the University of Limerick School of Medicine and a computational oncologist with over 20 years' experience in cancer genomics. Her expertise includes multi-omics data integration, statistical genomics,

and clinical bioinformatics, informed by more than 15 years at Dana-Farber Cancer Institute and Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health. Her research focuses on integrative analysis of single-cell cancer data, and she is a leader in the Bioconductor community and a strong advocate for open-source science.

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Luke Readman

Director of Digital Transformation, NHS
England, London

Topic: OneLondon - Past, Present and Future

Time: Monday, 26th January, 11:45-12:05

Speaker Profile: Luke Readman is a strategic digital leader with over 30 years' experience leading system- and organisation-level transformation across health and care, academia, and industry. A former practising radiographer, he has held senior board-level roles in digital, data, and technology, with a strong track record in large-scale service transformation, innovation, and knowledge transfer. His work focuses on using data and digital technologies to empower patients and professionals, improve care quality and outcomes, and drive sustainable health system change.

Professor Eva Morris

Professor of Health Data Epidemiology, University of
Oxford

Topic: Realising the potential of big data in cancer care: challenges and opportunities in the National Health Service

Time: Monday, 26th January, 12:05-12:25

Speaker Profile: Eva Morris is Professor of Health Data Epidemiology within the Big Data Institute and Oxford Population Health. She works in the field of health data research with a particularly strong interest in national cancer datasets. She is co-lead of the [HDR UK Oxford](#)

[Region](#), the NIHR Oxford Biomedical Research Centre's Translational Data Science theme and has a portfolio of highly applied research based around the use of linked NHS datasets to investigate the management and outcome of common diseases. She has a particular focus on colorectal cancer.

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Prof. Geoff Hall

Professor of Digital Health, University of Leeds

Topic: How can real-world evidence studies in cancer enhance clinical trials?

Time: Monday, 26th January, 12:25 - 12:45

Speaker Profile: Geoff Hall is Professor of Digital Health and Cancer Medicine at the University of Leeds and an Honorary Consultant Medical Oncologist at Leeds Cancer Centre. He is Chief Clinical Information Officer at Leeds Teaching Hospitals and Director of

DATA-CAN (HDR UK Cancer Hub), leading research in cancer informatics, data analytics, and multi-modal AI in ovarian cancer, and providing national clinical leadership in health data standards and trusted research environments.

Dr Stelios Theophanous

Real-World Data Analyst, University of Leeds, UK

Topic: Foundations in OMOP and Real-World Data: How to Run Your First Real-World Study

Time: Monday, 26th January, 14:30-17:30

Speaker Profile: Stelios is a Real-World Data Analyst at the University of Leeds, UK, transforming complex healthcare data into actionable insights. He specialises in federated learning, the OMOP Common Data Model, and multi-institutional real-world evidence studies.

Based at Leeds Teaching Hospitals NHS Trust, he leads the development of large-scale OMOP databases and applies privacy-preserving analytics to support clinical research and evidence-based decision-making.

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Dr Catherine Mahoney

Senior Advisor-HEOR & RWE Scientist, Eli Lilly

Topic: Foundations in OMOP and Real-World Data: How to Run Your First Real-World Study

Time: Monday, 26th January, 14:30-17:30

Speaker Profile: Catherine is a mathematician working in observational research at Eli Lilly, UK, with a PhD in Bioinformatics and Systems Biology from University College Dublin. Her research focuses on applying statistical and mathematical modelling to improve human health. She has experience across academia, government, and industry, and enjoys using quantitative approaches to tackle complex biological and social problems.

Prof. Dani Prieto-Alhambra

Professor of Pharmaco- & Device Epidemiology, University of Oxford

Topic: OMOP-based oncology research: from EHDEN to OPTIMA and GREG'

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 9:30-9:55

Speaker Profile: Dani (MD, MSc (Oxon), PhD) is a clinician scientist and Professor of Pharmacoepidemiology at the University of Oxford, with over 15 years' experience in pharmacoepidemiology and real-world evidence. Since 2022, he has served as Deputy Director of

the DARWIN EU initiative. He has published more than 420 papers (h-index 78) and has extensive expertise in using national and international real-world data to inform regulatory and HTA decision-making, as well as supervising PhD students and mentoring research staff.

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Dr Frances Burns

Northern Ireland Trusted Research Environment

Topic: The Northern Ireland Trusted Research Environment – an unrivalled opportunity

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 9:55-10:10

Speaker Profile: Dr Frances Burns is the lead for the Northern Ireland Trusted Research Environment (NITRE), part of the HSC data institute. She is co-founder and director of the Northern Ireland Public Data Panel (NIPDP), a cross sectional infrastructure for public dialogue on Northern Ireland. She is a member of the Understanding Patient Data steering group. She developed the Northern Ireland Cohort for the Longitudinal study of Aging, Northern Ireland's largest public health research project. She is an honorary lecturer in Queen's University Belfast Centre for Public Health from where she gained her PhD in research and impact pathways

Dr Christian Cole

Reader in Health Informatics, University of Dundee

Topic: Building Trusted Research Infrastructure in Scotland and the UK

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 10:10-10:25

Speaker Profile: Dr Christian Cole is Reader in Health Informatics at the University of Dundee, where he is Academic Co-Director of the Health Informatics Centre (HIC) and Director of the Alleviate Pain Data Hub. His research focuses on developing tools and infrastructure

for Trusted Research Environments, applying AI/ML to real-world healthcare data, and enabling federated, FAIR access to pain and other clinical datasets. He has been PI or Co-I on over £40m in research funding and has held leadership roles in data science and analysis across multiple centres.

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Abhishek Nayak PhD Candidate, eHealth-Hub, University of Limerick

Topic: Advancing Federated sharing of Cancer Clinical and Genomic Data Across Europe

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 10:25-10:35

Speaker Profile: Abhishek Nayak is a researcher at the University of Limerick with expertise in real-world evidence and observational health data analysis. He previously worked at Novartis as an RWE Scientific Data Analyst, where he supported real-world evidence generation using methods including survival analysis and health technology assessment to inform clinical and regulatory decision-making. His work bridges industry and academia, applying data-driven approaches to improve healthcare research.

Miriam Staunton Chairperson, UCAN Ireland

Topic: The importance of advocacy in shaping evidence, policy, and access pathways

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 11:30-11:45

Speaker Profile: Miriam Staunton is a stage IV melanoma survivor, diagnosed Stage III with no primary in 2018 Miriam progressed to stage IV a year later unable to access adjuvant treatment. With No evidence of disease since 2020 she has turned her focus to patient

advocacy focusing on access to clinical trials and cancer medications. Prior to her diagnosis she spent 25 years in the beverage industry in a number of technical roles. Miriam is an engineer by degree and has three adult children.

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Dr Katie Crowley

Associate Professor of Computer Science, University of Limerick

Topic: Designing EHDS-Ready Patient Portals for Trust, Accessibility and Empowerment in Cancer Care

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 11:45-12:00

Speaker Profile: Katie is an Associate Professor/Senior Lecturer in Computer Science at the University of Limerick and Course Director of the MSc in Health Informatics. Her research focuses on digital health transformation, patient-centred systems, participatory design, and connected health technologies. She leads multidisciplinary projects that bridge technology, healthcare, and industry collaboration.

Caitríona Wray

Assistant Principal Officer, Health Information Policy Unit

Topic: Health at our fingertips through digital public service delivery

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 12:00-12:15

Speaker Profile: Caitríona has over 25 years' experience in ICT and works within the Department of Health, where she serves as EU eHealth Project Coordinator. She has spent over a decade in the Department's eHealth Unit and now contributes to the Health Information Policy Unit, with a focus on the implementation of the

European Health Data Space and the secondary use of health data. Her work is patient-centred, supporting the delivery of robust national and cross-border eHealth services, including EU cross-border healthcare for Irish citizens and the myHealth@myHands project.

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Amy Nolan

Director of Clinical Affairs', The Irish Cancer Society

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 12:15-12:30

Speaker Profile: Amy Nolan is Director of Clinical Affairs at the Irish Cancer Society and a member of its Executive Leadership Team. She leads clinical engagement, institutional partnerships, and the Society's research and Children, Adolescents & Young Adults (CAYA) programmes.

A Fellow of the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, she has a background in oncology nursing and is recognised for developing innovative, patient-centred services and education initiatives.

Professor Michael Quinn

Professor of Practice, Queens University Belfast

Topic: Encompass – a digital transformation but it's only the start!

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 12:30-12:45

Speaker Profile: Michael is an NHS Consultant, CCIO, and clinical academic at Queen's University Belfast with expertise in healthcare data privacy, governance, and EHR implementation. He combines clinical, commercial, and academic experience to ensure healthcare data is used safely and effectively, while maximising the value of digital health systems.

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Professor Ruth Clifford

Consultant Hematologist, University Hospital Limerick

Topic: Connecting Blood Cancer Data to Improve Patient Outcomes

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 12:45-13:05

Speaker Profile: Professor Ruth Clifford is a Consultant Haematologist at UHL, specialising in lymphoid malignancies including chronic lymphocytic leukaemia (CLL). Her research focuses on genetic drivers of blood cancers, mechanisms of relapse and resistance, and the application of novel technologies and AI to improve diagnosis and clinical trial access. She holds a PhD from the University of Oxford, where her work identified a gene mutation in SAMHD1 predicting chemotherapy resistance in CLL, and she maintains active collaborations in haematology genomics research nationally and internationally.

Dr. Joep de Ligt

Data Lead, Hartwig Medical Foundation, Netherlands

Topic: Cancer Genomics in the Netherlands; Predicting non-response and the Implementation of OMOP

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 14:15-14:35

Speaker Profile: Joep de Ligt holds a PhD in molecular life science and is a genomics and bioinformatics expert currently leading the Data activities at the Hartwig Medical Foundation in the Netherlands. He has led and advised national and international health genomics

efforts in human and pathogen genomics and was the driving force behind the genomics effort to sequence more than 80% of cases in the COVID-19 response in Aotearoa New Zealand. His work focuses on translating complex data into actionable insights for human health.

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Professor Richard Kennedy

Global Vice President, Biomarker Development and Medical Director, Almac Diagnostic Services

Topic: Precision Oncology: What's the reality?

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 14:35-14:55

Speaker Profile: Richard Kennedy is Global VP and Medical Director at Almac and Professor of Oncology at Queen's University Belfast. He trained as a medical oncologist, holds a PhD in Molecular Biology, and leads precision medicine research and clinical biomarker development. He serves on advisory panels including MATRIX NI and the Royal College of Physicians Oncology Advisory Group.

Brendan Reardon

Post-Grad, Dana Farber Cancer Institute and University of Limerick

Topic: Towards an All-Island Precision Oncology Knowledge Base

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 14:55-15:10

Speaker Profile: Brendan Reardon is a graduate student with Aedin Culhane within University of Limerick's School of Medicine. His research focuses on developing computational tools for the clinical and biological

interpretation of genomic variants in cancer. He is also a computational scientist in the Van Allen lab at Dana-Farber Cancer Institute.

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Sarah Hersey

Vice President Precision Medicine, Bristol Myers Squibb

Topic: Precision Medicine: What's so difficult?

Time: Tuesday, 27th January, 15:10-15:25

Speaker Profile: Sarah has over 20 years' experience leading R&D organisations, CLIA and GLP laboratories, device manufacturing, and technology strategy in precision medicine and companion diagnostics. She is currently at BMS and previously founded the Precision Medicine Organisation at Celgene, following senior leadership roles at Novartis, where her teams achieved multiple

health authority approvals including the first pre-market approval for a distributable NGS companion diagnostic, and at Johnson & Johnson. She is also a strong advocate for education and awareness in precision medicine and in vitro diagnostics.

